

SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL BASIS OF TRAINING OF QUALIFIED COACHES FOR OLYMPIC AND PARALYMPIC

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Abstract. This article examines the scientific and methodological basis of training qualified coaches in Olympic and Paralympic sports. The study of scientific and methodological bases in the training of coaches is of great importance in the development of sports. This article shows the important basics and their place in the training of coaches of Olympic and Paralympic sports. The article serves to provide an overview of the scientific and methodological foundations of training coaches and their role in the learning, development and success of athletes.

Keywords: Olympics, Paralympics, coach, scientific research, theoretical foundations.

НАУЧНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ПОДГОТОВКИ КВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ТРЕНЕРОВ ДЛЯ ОЛИМПИЙСКИХ И ПАРАЛИМПИЙСКИХ ИГР

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются научно-методические основы подготовки квалифицированных тренеров по олимпийским и паралимпийским видам спорта. Изучение научно-методических основ подготовки тренеров имеет большое значение в развитии спорта. В данной статье показаны важные основы и их место в подготовке тренеров олимпийских и паралимпийских видов спорта. Статья призвана дать обзор научно-методических основ подготовки тренеров и их роли в обучении, развитии и успехе спортсменов.

Ключевые слова: Олимпиада, Паралимпийские игры, тренер, научные исследования, теоретические основы.

An important part of the study of the scientific-methodical basis of training qualified coaches in Olympic and Paralympic sports, scientific research, interdisciplinary discussions, and theoretical foundations related to this path. These types may be related to fields in sports psychology, biomechanics, residential design, and other fields. Concepts, methods and techniques are learned and developed based on experiential practices.

In order to study the scientific-methodical basis of training coaches for Olympic and Paralympic sports, attention is paid to the following main areas:

1. Sports Science and Theory: Studying the specific science and theory of Olympic and Paralympic sports is essential. In this, the basic principles, rules, history, and research of the sport are studied in general.

2. Biomechanics: This field deals with the movements of athletes, their strength characteristics and the scientific basis of movement development.

3. Sports Psychology: Olympic and Paralympic coaches study psychological techniques to improve athletes' psychological skills in motivating, rewarding, stress management and goal orientation.

4. Housing Design: This area is very important for coaches because their athletes need comfortable, responsible and healthy housing during their training period.

5. Medicine and Health: Analysis of sports medicine, scientific methods in testing and injury, and learning about important health issues for athletes.

6. Social and Cultural Factors: Olympic and Paralympic sports involve a social and cultural environment. Coaches learn to understand the social stratum and follow the financial, social and cultural indicators of the athletes.

Coaches well trained in these areas help athletes improve their external and internal performance, increase their strength and reach their highest potential. In order to make the scientific and methodological basis of training coaches of Olympic and Paralympic sports more, the following points can be paid attention to:

1. Interdisciplinarity: A key part of the study of Olympic and Paralympic sports is the integration of scientific research from different fields. Ideas from biomechanics, sports psychology, pedagogy, medicine, and other fields are interrelated and are used for complex study and counseling of coaches.

2. Consolidation of Practical Action: Consolidation of theory in practice and study and development of the scientific basis of working with athletes. Practical skills and learning methods are of great importance in the teaching process in classes and sports organizations.

3. Experienced Coaching: It is important to have the influence of experienced Olympic and Paralympic athletes and coaches in training Olympic and Paralympic sports coaches. They influence new poke generations by making their learning and experience a key part of coaching.

4. Research-Based Practices: Another skill in training Olympic and Paralympic sports coaches is to put ideas and skills into practice through research-based practices. It plays an important role in creating new scientific achievements and new sports skills.

5. Creative Approach: A creative approach should be included in the scientific and methodological basis of training coaches of Olympic and Paralympic sports. Creating new methods, techniques and programs is important in the development of coaching itself

To learn more about the scientific and methodological basis of training coaches of Olympic and Paralympic sports, pay attention to the following path:

1. Academic Olympic and Paralympic Journals: These journals provide scholarly research on Olympic and Paralympic sports. Magazine sites may contain lists, articles, and news.

2. Universities and Institutes in Olympic and Paralympic Sports: Several universities and institutes offer classes and courses to study, conduct research and train coaches in Olympic and Paralympic sports. Information on the scientific and methodological basis of Olympic and Paralympic sports can be found on their websites.

3. Conferences and Events Dedicated to Olympic and Paralympic Sports: Following them provides a good opportunity to keep up with the latest scientific and practical achievements of Olympic and Paralympic sports.

4. Scientific Journals and Books: Scientific journals and books devoted to Olympic and Paralympic sports are good sources for learning the scientific and methodological basis of training coaches.

5. Scientific Conferences and Seminars: These events provide a good opportunity to learn about the latest scientific achievements, new methods and techniques related to Olympic and Paralympic sports.

These changing relationships are critical to athletes' self-improvement and success.

The importance of the coach in Olympic and Paralympic sports is very high. They do a great job of learning, developing and bringing athletes to the highest level of their sport. The position of the coach can be indicated in the following directions:

1. Coach: Coaches are important guides in the learning and development of athletes. They provide scientific and practical support to athletes, teach them various sports techniques and become their guards.

2. Mentor: Coaches take on the role of mentoring athletes in implementing what they have learned or solving problems that arise in sports. Their experience and performance is very important in helping athletes.

3. Motivator: Coaches play a major role in motivating athletes to maintain progress, set high goals, and reach the top of their sport.

4. Psychologist: Coaches are also very important in helping athletes in the field of sports psychology. They need experience and knowledge to free athletes from stress, depression, and other psychological problems.

5. Entrepreneur: Coaches help develop entrepreneurship for athletes and create more unique parts of their sport. They provide athletes with additional advice and creative experiences.

The role of coaches is very important in Olympic and Paralympic sports. Their roles and responsibilities in the learning and development of athletes are huge for athletes.

Also, the role of the relationship between the athlete and the coach in sports will bring strength to your life. A coach, as an instructor, can help an athlete achieve the skills, motivation, and comfort necessary for success.

The athlete develops himself under the guidance and guidance of the coach and helps to achieve his goals. These relationships provide not only physical, but also mental and spiritual development in sports.

To be more specific, a person called an "Athlete" may have a direction or a mission to show a person called a "coach" or "trainer".

1. Coach: This person advises the athlete, helps him to develop himself and supervises him well. It teaches artistic, tactical, and mental skills for the athlete in his early years.

2. Athlete: This person, who aims to develop himself in sports, used the guidance of a coach or trainer to achieve this path. He implements the advice given by the coach and develops in the direction indicated by him. This relationship can exist at any level of the sport, but usually the relationship between the artistic athlete and the instructor appears in many practices in youth, practicing gyms or clubbers. Competing, focused and careful, a firm bridge with his coach or trainer must be established.

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